

A Study on the Impact of Bancassurance in Indian Economy

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Introduction :

The banking and insurance industry have changed rapidly in the changing economic environment throughout the world. Together Banking and Insurance Industry contributes about seven percent GDP of our economy. The increased pace of market competition due to liberalization and privatization forced life insurers to be competitive by cutting cost and serving in a better way to the customers. In view to reach huge untapped market, the concept of Bancassurance was introduced by the IRDA. Bancassurance is a new and an emerging model of channel of distribution adopted by almost all the life insurance players to increase the market share and insurance penetration. The present empirical based study was conducted with an objective to understand the role of bancassurance in Indian life Insurance Industry and to measure customer awareness, satisfaction and perception towards buying life insurance products from banks.

Definition :

Bancassurance arrangement benefits both the firms. On the one hand, the bank earns fee amount (non-interest income) from the insurance company apart from the interest income whereas on the other hand, the insurance firm increases its market reach and customers. The bank acts as an intermediary, helping insurance firm reach its target customer in order to increase its market share.

Historical Background :

The concept of Bancassurance gained importance in the growing global insurance industry and its search for new channels of distribution. It has been very successful in Europe, especially France and Portugal, wherein as much as 70% of the insurance products are sold through the Banking Channels alone followed by Spain where more than 60% of the insurance products are being sold through the Banks. These countries are stated to be most successful in Bancassurance. In Italy, though the Bancassurance concept has been in prevalence for some years but picked up only since the late 1990s. As opposed to the above, in the UK and the Netherlands the concept of Bancassurance slated to be relatively less popular although banks sell the insurance products there also.

Recent Trends of Bancassurance :

1. Bancassurers have not only targeted the mass market but have also carefully begun to segment the market which has resulted in the tailor - made or rather perfect products for each segment.
2. Some Bancassurers focus exclusively on distribution. In some markets, face-to-face contact is preferred which proves to be a favorable arrangement for the development of Bancassurance business.
3. Initially banks opt for either “referral models” or “corporate agency”.
4. Banks are offering space in their own premises to accommodate the insurance staff for selling the insurance products or giving access to their client’s database. Insurance companies can use this opportunity to increase their sale.

Benefits of Bancassurance: An Analysis

➤ **For Banks :**

The first and the foremost benefit is that the banks get an additional product in their basket to reduce their risk of regular income. Secondly, by selling the insurance products, they tend to gain additional income in the form of fees. Thirdly, the banks will get to retain the customers with wider relationship with them by providing them a comprehensive service of banking and insurance at a single window.

➤ **For Insurance Company :**

Selling their products through banks gave them access to the wide rural market. Many public sector banks have branches in the remote rural areas, these acts as a ready untapped market for the insurance companies at a nominal cost. The insurance companies could reach out to the highly endowed and growing middle class section of the society through the banks distribution network.

➤ **For Customers :**

The Bancassurance model assists in terms of reduction price, diversified product quality in time, all services under one-roof and service at their doorstep service by banks. Innovative and better product ranges and products designed as per the needs of customers. Customers could also get a share in the cost savings in the form of reduced premium rate because of economies of scope, besides getting better financial counseling at single point.

Business Models of Bancassurance :

Various models have been developed based on the level of integration and the importance sought by the two players. Joint Venture and third-party distribution partners are both popular Bancassurance models in India.

- ***Distribution Agreements*** : The Bank personnel sell the products of one insurer exclusively, either in standalone basis or bundle with bank products.
- ***Joint Venture*** : A large bank with a well-developed customer database partners with a large insurer with strong product and channel experience, to develop a powerful new distribution model.

Conclusion :

India has a much better chance to succeed in bancassurance business due to the fact that the banking operations in India are still branch oriented and manually operated in semi-urban and villages, unlike in other developed countries of the world. The Regulatory Authorities in India may explore the possibility of allowing commercial banks to have tie-up arrangements for bancassurance business with more than one insurance company. The Bancassurance business of private sector bank is at the infant stage, as it's not producing much revenue for the banks. So there is a need for private sector banks to frame such policies and products which could increase their bancassurance income. Such Programmed needs to be organized, which would make the customer aware about the bancassurance products of the banks.

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